

Assessing Shielding Materials for Compliance with ICNIRP Recommendations Regarding Exposure to Electromagnetic Radiation from Mobile Devices

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Abstract: The phenomenon of radio frequency electromagnetic energy emitted from mobile phones is widely recognized, and the specific absorption rate (SAR) measures the amount of energy absorbed by the human head. To meet SAR standards, mobile phones can be shielded. This paper utilizes COMSOL Multiphysics to model the human head and simulate SAR distribution for various head layers exposed to radiation from a CDMA 800 downlink frequency band mobile phone. The study also observes electric and magnetic fields across the frequency range and investigate five different shielding materials. The results reveal that a polyimide sheet outperforms other materials according to ICNIRP guidelines for electromagnetic radiation exposure. These findings have significant implications for the design and production of mobile phones, as well as public health and safety.

Index Terms - Specific absorption rate (SAR); Shielding materials; Human head modeling; Polyimide shielding; Mobile phone radiation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of mobile phones has raised concerns about potential health risks from exposure to radio frequency electromagnetic energy [1]. The human body is continually exposed to electromagnetic waves from various devices, including cell phones and wireless routers, which may result in health hazards such as brain tumors, childhood leukemia, miscarriage, cardiovascular effects, Alzheimer's disease, genotoxic effects, breast cancer, DNA damage, and micro nucleation [2]. Nevertheless, scientists are still debating the actual risks associated with exposure to electromagnetic radiation as some studies suggest a link between RF exposure and specific health hazards while others have found no conclusive association [3]. The Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) is a measure of the energy absorbed by the human head when exposed to mobile phone radiation, and the International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP) has established guidelines to restrict the exposure of the human body to radio frequency energy. Identify the constructs of a Journal – Essentially a journal consists of five major sections [4-5].

CDMA 800 is a type of digital wireless communication technology that employs spread spectrum techniques to facilitate multiple users sharing the same frequency band. Its operational frequency range is from 824 MHz to 894 MHz, within the 800 MHz frequency band [6]. CDMA 800 works by utilizing two frequency bands; the uplink frequency range between 824 MHz and 849 MHz and the downlink frequency range between 869 MHz and 894 MHz. This technology is renowned for its superior call quality, enhanced capacity, and advanced security features compared to earlier analog cellular systems. As one of the earliest versions of Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA) technology, CDMA 800 has been widely deployed in North America, Asia, and other regions of the world [7].

Mobile phones can be shielded to comply with SAR standards and minimize radio frequency energy exposure to the human head. However, the effectiveness of different shielding materials in reducing SAR is uncertain. In 2009, Islam et al. conducted a study using the FDTD method with the Lossy-Drude model to investigate the reduction of Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) by attaching a ferrite sheet to the human head. The study analyzed various factors, including attachment location, distance, size, and material properties of the ferrite sheet, on SAR reduction. The results indicated that attaching the ferrite sheet in the optimal location and distance could significantly reduce SAR, achieving a reduction of 57.75% for SAR_{10gm} [8]. In 2011, Faruque et al. conducted a study to evaluate the effectiveness of using materials and metamaterials for reducing the Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) in mobile phones. The study employed the finite-difference time-domain method with the lossy-Drude model to investigate the SAR reduction achieved by attaching materials like ferrite sheets, perfect electric conductor (PEC), and metamaterials of varying sizes and positions. The findings of the study indicate that both materials and metamaterials can significantly reduce SAR. However, metamaterials were found to provide a slightly higher reduction in SAR compared to materials [9]. El Amrani, Mazri, and Hmina (2017) emphasize the significance of electromagnetic field modeling in analyzing potential health effects on the human body. While some laboratory studies have suggested harmful effects of electromagnetic waves, others have dismissed these hypotheses. Their paper is a follow-up to their previous work that aimed to model the specific absorption rate (SAR) of radio waves in the human body caused by exposure to wireless base station fields.

However, in this study, they utilize measurements taken by an EM radiation meter [10]. In 2019, Messaoudi, Hafawa & Aguilu conducted a study to evaluate the possible application of metamaterials in reducing the Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) of RF electromagnetic radiation from mobile phone handsets in the human head. The authors highlight the growing concern among the public about the potential health hazards linked with exposure to RF radiation as a result of the widespread use of wireless communication systems. The paper presents a review of different SAR reduction techniques, including metamaterials, ferrite sheets, conductive materials, frequency selective surfaces, and electromagnetic bandgap structures [11]. In 2022, Hediya et al. conducted a comprehensive review of different techniques employed for reducing Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) in antennas. The authors emphasize that no individual technique can effectively achieve desirable results for all parameters at once, and the selection of SAR reduction techniques largely depends on the specific application. The paper reviews various techniques such as reflectors, RF shielding, and the design of directive antennas [12].

This study, using COMSOL Multiphysics, modeled the human head and simulated the Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) distribution for different head layers exposed to radiation from a mobile phone operating at the CDMA 800 downlink frequency band. Unlike most SAR reduction studies, which rely on the Finite-Difference Time-Domain (FDTD) method, this research used the Finite Element Method (FEM) to calculate electromagnetic parameters. Additionally, the study observed the electric and magnetic fields across the frequency range and evaluated five different shielding materials. The results suggest that a polyimide sheet is the most effective material for complying with ICNIRP guidelines for radio frequency exposure. The study provides important insights into the potential health impacts of radio frequency electromagnetic energy on the human body and highlights the significance of proper shielding in mobile phone design for public health and safety.

II. DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The COMSOL software utilizes a homogenous human head model based on the IEEE, IEC, and CENELEC Specified Anthropomorphic Mannequin (SAM) Phantom, which is a standard specification for SAR value measurements. The head phantom model was created using an MRI image with 109 slices, each consisting of 256×256 voxels [13]. The final model incorporates realistic dimensions and consists of two separate models: one for the antenna and another for the head. To combine these models into a unified computational domain, a spherical geometry is used, which also includes the surrounding air. The patch antenna board has dimensions of 8cm in length, 8cm in breadth, and 4mm in thickness. The human head model has a nearby shielding material sheet designed with dimensions of 9cm in length, 9cm in width, and 1.5mm in thickness (d_c). Fig. 1(a) and (b) illustrate the top view and side view of the simulation's design setup.

Figure 1 a) Top view and b) Side view of three dimensional human head phantom model with the shielding sheet and patch antenna board of a mobile phone.

Table 1 Materials' general and electrical characteristics used in simulation

Material	Relative Permittivity, ϵ_r	Conductivity, σ (S/m)	Density, ρ (kg/m ³)
Printed Circuit Board	5.23	0.05	--
Brain Tissue	56	1.35	1030
Blood	61.4	1.54	1000
Silver	4.3	6.3×10^7	10490
Aluminium	1.6	3.5×10^7	2689
Teflon	2.1	10^{-25}	2250
Mica	6	10^{-16}	3100
Polyimide	3.4	10^{-18}	1420

III. NUMERICAL METHODOLOGY

The potential impact of electromagnetic waves on human health is currently a topic of discussion and research. In order to assist these research efforts, numerical simulations of electromagnetic wave absorption and the resulting tissue heating can be valuable tools [14]. The focus of the current work is to use the finite element method (FEM) to simulate the absorption of electromagnetic waves caused by cell phone use and the resulting temperature increase in the human skull, which includes skin-fat, bone, and brain tissues. COMSOL Multiphysics is used to support vector elements in triangular and tetrahedral models. The nonhomogeneous electromagnetic wave equations in the frequency domain are solved to carry out the electromagnetic field analysis [15].

$$\nabla \times (1/\mu_r \nabla \times \bar{E}) - k_0^2 [\epsilon_r - \frac{i\sigma}{\omega\epsilon_0}] \bar{E} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Where k_0 is the free space wave number, \bar{E} is the complex strength of wave number, ϵ_r is the relative electric permittivity and μ_r relative magnetic permeability.

The rate at which energy is absorbed by the human body when exposed to a radio frequency (RF) electromagnetic field is measured as SAR. It is defined as follows [16]:

$$SAR = \frac{\sigma}{2\rho} \bar{E}^2 \quad (\text{W/kg}) \quad (2)$$

Where σ is the body tissue conductivity (S/m), ρ is the body tissue density (kg/m³), and E is the RMS value of the electric field strength in the tissue (V/m). SAR tests are only performed for 6 minutes of mobile phone usage; however studies have shown that individuals use mobile phones for several hours [17].

The spatial average of local exposure for general public SAR limit is 2 W/kg over 10g of tissues, according to ICNIRP standards [18]. To avoid negative impacts on human health, SAR values must not exceed the threshold limits. The SAR Reduction Factor (SRF) is defined as follows [19]:

$$SRF_{10g} (\%) = \frac{SAR_{10g} - SAR_{10g,s}}{SAR_{10g}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Where SRF_{10g} is SAR reduction factor for 10g peak SAR, SAR_{10g} is 10g peak SAR without shielding and $SAR_{10g,s}$ is 10g peak SAR with shielding.

IV. NUMERICAL OUTCOMES AND DISCUSSION

Using the finite element method, the electric field, magnetic field, and specific absorption rate (SAR) values were obtained after analyzing the electromagnetic field with respect to frequency. Fig. 2 shows the relationship between frequency and SAR values, with the CDMA downlink frequency ranging from 869 MHz to 894 MHz. Five materials were examined across this range, including two metals (aluminium and silver) and three non-metals (Teflon/PTFE, mica, and polyimide). The SAR level for silver sheet ranged from 4.332 to 5.761 W/kg over 10g of tissue, which is nearly twice the allowed value. The SAR level for aluminium sheet ranged from 1.111 to 1.477 W/kg over 10g of tissue, which is around half of the maximum exposure value. The SAR level for mica and Teflon sheets ranged from 0.501 to 0.6568 W/kg and 0.4312 to 0.5649 W/kg respectively over 10g of tissue, which also suggests their suitability for SAR reduction. The SAR value for polyimide sheet ranged from 0.1684 to 0.2206 W/kg over 10g of tissue, indicating that polyimide effectively reduces the SAR value and performs better than the other materials in terms of reducing local RF exposure.

Figure 2 Frequency vs. Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) plot for different shielding materials.

The electric field analysis of five different materials using the CDMA downlink frequency range is presented in Fig. 3. The electric field values for aluminum and silver shielding sheets show a very similar range across the frequency spectrum, from 0.02474 V/m to 0.02852 V/m. Teflon and mica have electric fields that range from 0.01685 V/m to 0.01929 V/m and 0.01547 V/m to 0.01772 V/m, respectively. The polyimide sheet displays lower electric field ranges ranging from 0.01325 V/m to 0.01517 V/m. These findings suggest that mica, Teflon, and polyimide offer less susceptibility to electric fields. However, polyimide can provide stronger electric field shielding than other materials. According to ICNIRP standards [20], the reference levels for local exposure to incident electric field strength from 100 kHz to 10 MHz (unperturbed rms values) are 170 V/m for occupational exposure and 83 V/m for general public exposure. This study takes into account the electric field strength of 83 V/m for mobile phones and local exposure criteria. The values obtained in this study appear to be lower than the ICNIRP guidelines.

Figure 3 Frequency vs. Electric Field plot for different shielding materials.

The graph in Fig. 4 shows the magnetic field analysis of five materials using the CDMA downlink frequency range. The magnetic field ranges for aluminium and silver shielding sheets are very similar, ranging from 35.5 μ T to 38.86 μ T across the frequency spectrum. Teflon and mica have magnetic field ranges of 35.23 μ T to 38.27 μ T and 35.27 μ T to 38.33 μ T, respectively. The polyimide sheet has lower magnetic field ranges, ranging from 35.25 μ T to 38.3 μ T. The ICNIRP standards provide reference levels for local exposure to incident magnetic field strength from 100 kHz to 10 MHz (unperturbed rms values). These standards suggest that the reference levels for occupational exposure should be 100.53 μ T, while the levels for general public exposure should be 26.39 μ T. This study uses the ICNIRP guideline of 26.39 μ T for magnetic field strength from mobile phones, and local exposure criteria [21]. The magnetic field values obtained from the study are slightly higher than the ICNIRP guidelines, but still fall within a reasonable range.

Figure 4 Frequency vs. Magnetic Field plot for different shielding materials.

Figure 5 Electromagnetic field distribution for different material shielding.

Fig. 5 illustrates the distribution of electromagnetic fields across the human head for different types of shielding materials. It is evident from the graph that metallic shielding, such as aluminum or silver shielding causes more spreading of the electromagnetic field compared to non-metallic shielding materials.

Table 2 SAR reduction factor for various materials at 894 MHz operating frequency

Shielding Materials	SAR without shielding for 10g peak SAR, SAR_{10g} (ICNIRP standard value for local exposure) W/kg	SAR with shielding for 10g peak SAR, $SAR_{10g,s}$ W/kg	SAR reduction factor for 10g peak SAR, $SRF_{10g}(\%)$
Silver	2	5.761	N/A
Aluminium	2	1.477	26.15%
Teflon	2	0.5649	71.76%
Mica	2	0.6568	67.16%
Polyimide	2	0.2206	88.97%

Table 2 displays the SAR reduction factor for different materials at an operating frequency of 894 MHz. This frequency was selected to assess the SAR reduction level for different shielding materials. The SAR value of 2 W/kg was considered as the ICNIRP standard value for local RF exposure for 10g peak SAR in the absence of any shielding. The results show that the SAR value for the silver sheet did not decrease even after applying various types of shielding. On the other hand, polyimide had the highest SAR reduction factor, with a reduction of 88.97%.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RECOMMENDATION

The objective of this research was to assess the effectiveness of various shielding materials for mobile phones in meeting the ICNIRP guidelines for exposure to electromagnetic radiation. The study employed the finite element method and COMSOL Multiphysics to model the human head and simulate the distribution of SAR for different head layers exposed to radiation from a CDMA 800 downlink frequency band mobile phone. The study also analyzed the electric and magnetic fields across a broad frequency range for five different shielding materials. The results showed that the polyimide sheet outperformed other materials in terms of meeting the ICNIRP guidelines for exposure to electromagnetic radiation. These findings have significant implications for public health and safety as well as the design and production of mobile phones. Effective shielding materials can reduce the amount of electromagnetic radiation absorbed by the human head while also ensuring compliance with international safety standards. In future studies, the dimensions of shielding materials, such as thickness, can be modified to achieve better reduction. The research will also extend to various cellular frequency bands and technologies, including 2G, 3G, 4G LTE, and 5G.

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